

Framework for collaborative human-robot flexible manufacturing applications

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Abstract—A growing number of robots collaborating closely with human operators is envisaged to be employed in manufacturing assembly lines in the next future. It has been demonstrated in many research works that robots increase the productivity and efficiency of the manufacturing process. However, safety is a challenging problem to be considered in human-robot collaborative applications. This work outlines a flexible human-robot collaborative framework, which is the core of a brand new project to be fully developed in the very next future, to provide intuitive and safe human-robot interactions, leveraging mobile robots and manipulators.

Index Terms—Flexible manufacturing, human-robot collaboration, mobile robotics

I. INTRODUCTION

The 4th industrial revolution converged in the integration of technological advances that led to a morphological change of the production/assembly line implementation, due to the upheaval of its very concept inevitably dictated by market demand [1]. In particular, custom manufacturing can help Small and Medium-sized Enterprises (SMEs) as it favours decentralized solutions. In fact, human manual operations should be systematically enhanced through the collaboration with robots, in order to improve the overall efficiency. To this end, Human-Robot Collaboration (HRC) should guarantee an effective and safe interaction between the human operator and the robot (mobile or fixed-base cobot), in order to value the cognitive capabilities and experience-based knowledge of the former and the accuracy, strength and efficiency of the latter.

One way to achieve safe interaction in HRC applications is to improve the robot perception system that gathers and processes meaningful data from sensors, monitoring both the environment and human actions. Most of the techniques used to filter and classify the data is based on Artificial Intelligence (AI) algorithms, which combine in an efficient way several data types from different sensors [2], so as to make the robot more aware of its surroundings and be able to correct its actions depending on the scenario. Nevertheless, AI-based methods require a lot of data for the training and validation phase. In addition, in order to achieve higher precision, the sensors required for a specific application may be expensive and therefore, they might not be feasible for a real implementation in industry. Another way to guarantee safety in human-robot shared workspaces might be to improve the motion

planning of the robot using the on-board sensory system and considering the human operator's tasks.

Human-in-the-loop (HITL) collaborative applications features are affected by the required degree of collaboration, defined by the product characteristics and the human operator attributes, e.g., working quality and age-related performance results. As anthropocentric approaches are envisaged to become the core of future factories [3], the key feature of the described systems should be the adaptability of robots.

II. PROPOSED APPROACH

Let us consider a custom manufacturing plant where flexible production lines are composed of human operators, and both fixed-base and mobile robots. Specifically, the robotic system collaborating with the human operator can take on the role of trainee, i.e., it autonomously learns and becomes aware of the executed operation or task, exploiting information about the human counterpart (Figure 1). Then, given a collaborative operation, the robotic system should act proactively to maximize execution effectiveness, efficiency, and safety.

Fig. 1. A robot-assisted assembly use case. The human operator needs to carry out several tasks performed at ad-hoc workstations, monitored and assisted by the robotic system.

The proposed framework idea is based on making the robotic system able to (i) autonomously recognize the executed process, i.e., the operation (a set of tasks) or the task, and (ii) plan and re-plan its motion to carry out safely the operation. In particular, the current framework focuses on the role of Autonomous Mobile Robots (AMRs) and mobile manipulators, since little research has been carried out on mobile robotics involved in HITL collaborative applications, presumably due to the lack of specific safety regulations for mobile-cobots.

At a higher level, the framework utilises the human operator information to learn a model for process recognition, and determines the robotic system action based on the recognition result, to allow anticipatory behaviour. This could reduce waiting times of the human operator during the interaction with the robot, allowing for minimization of the overall process execution time, hence of the execution efficiency.

The high-level functions can be summarized as follows:

- (i) *Human operator modeling.* The human operator is approximated by a 2D point on the plant map with the aim of performing the operation recognition based on the trajectory data.
- (ii) *Data collection.* Data collection is performed by a robotic system, serving as a distributed network of sensors.
- (iii) *Robotic system awareness.* The mobile platform is capable of identifying the human operator position [4] (Figure 2) and implementing a collaborative behaviour, as envisioned in [5]. The human operator motion between workstations of the flexible production line (operation execution) is mapped to production operations, according to a trajectory classification algorithm based on machine learning or deep learning clustering methods. A robot reference trajectory is associated to each operation.
- (iv) *Robotic system control.* The reference trajectory corresponding to the identified operation is used for controlling the autonomous mobile platform or manipulator, enabling a sort of prediction of the human expected behaviour.

Fig. 2. Human detection and relative virtual obstacle, which covers the whole detected person bounding box.

Moreover, at the interaction level, safety can be guaranteed through a path planning algorithm that computes a consistent trajectory for the AMR forcing it to follow a virtual safe path, which can be easily predicted by the human operators. In [6], the algorithm has one additional level of hierarchy with respect

to traditional path planners. Indeed, the supervisory planner generates a path and sends the information to the global and local planners of the robot. The navigation algorithm was improved later by updating the path computation when some important or critical events are detected [7], e.g., a human crossing the robot in motion. As a result, the local planner closes a loop with the supervisory level, so a new path (similar to the original one) is computed and transmitted to the robot.

On the other hand, ensuring safety on mobile manipulators is more challenging since safety guidelines for mobile cobots are not yet available. However, if the manipulator is a cobot and the mobile platform has safe mechanisms, it could be assumed as a safe system. Safe motion planning for collaborative manipulation tasks could be achieved, for example, generating customized paths and grasping modes depending on the dangerousness of the object to be delivered directly to the human operator. For instance, intrinsic parameters of the robot, such as stiffness or flexibility, could be exploited in the dynamic model to avoid damages even when (in the worst case) there are unintentional collisions.

III. CONCLUSIONS

The introduced framework aims at improving collaborative human-robot flexible manufacturing processes. Given the future trends, it is clear that a strong focus should be put on implementing efficient and safe mobile robotics HITL applications. Therefore, combining a complex perception system for operations and tasks recognition, and manipulating some intrinsic parameters of the dynamical model of the robot might enhance the awareness of the robotic system while performing tasks that require direct contact with a human operator, providing a more aware and safer behaviour in HRC.

The authors future works will focus on the implementation of the framework, after accurate investigation of the most suitable methods to achieve the desired behaviour.

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